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**CRITERIA FOR IMPROVING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF CRIMINAL LAWS
IN PREVENTING CRIMINAL OFFENSES****Inna ROSHCHINA,**
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The article examines topical problems of increasing the effectiveness of criminal law in the prevention of criminal offenses. In order to improve the scientific level and quality of the preparation of legislative acts, it is proposed to adopt the Law «On the criminological examination of draft laws».

Key words: criminal law, prevention, norm, efficiency, criminal offense.

**КРИТЕРИИ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ НОРМ УГОЛОВНОГО ПРАВА
В ПРЕДУПРЕЖДЕНИИ УГОЛОВНЫХ ПРАВОНАРУШЕНИЙ****Инна Анатольевна РОЩИНА,**
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В статье исследованы актуальные проблемы повышения эффективности норм уголовного права в предупреждении уголовных правонарушений. С целью повышения научного уровня и качества подготовки законодательных актов предлагается принять Закон «О криминологической экспертизе законопроектов».

Ключевые слова: уголовное право, предупреждение, норма, эффективность, уголовное правонарушение.

Formulation of the problem. Crime as a mass phenomenon and a social problem is causing growing concern not only in Ukraine, but throughout the world.

In 2020, all law enforcement agencies registered 784,096 criminal offenses in Ukraine, which is slightly less than in previous years (for example: in 2019 - 840,447). At the same time, the statistical indicators given in the analysis for the past six years, especially for 2017-2020, raise reasonable doubts, be-

cause the real situation with the commission of criminal offenses in our country is really getting worse, not improving [1].

According to the service Numbeo, which forms the Crime Index, Ukraine as of 2021 ranks 54th in the world (out of 135) in terms of crime. In Europe, according to this indicator, our country was in third place after Belarus and France [2].

Particularly alarming is organized crime, which has remained one of the greatest

threats to Ukraine's political and economic development for at least the past few decades.

According to the rating of the Global Organized Crime Index, Ukraine took 34th position. Experts assessed it as a country with a high crime rate and low ability of the authorities to resist it, according to the report of the Global Initiative against Transnational Organized Crime for 2021 [3].

Therefore, effective counteraction to organized crime requires extraordinary attention from the community. However, organized criminal activity in Ukraine practically remains without adequate opposition from the state authorities, since there is more imitation in such activities than real steps.

An example in this regard is the Law "On the Application of Personal Special Economic and Other Restrictive Measures (Sanctions)" signed by the President of Ukraine on May 14, 2021. This law allows the imposition of sanctions before the so-called "thieves in law" without proving the guilt of these persons in committing specific criminal offenses, and even more so without convictions by the courts, which is a manifestation of legal nihilism and a violation of the rule of law. Such laws will not have a preventive value for criminal offenses.

Part 1 of Art. 1 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine (Tasks of the Criminal Code of Ukraine) states that "The Criminal Code of Ukraine has as its task the legal provision of the protection of human and civil rights and freedoms, property, public order and public safety, the environment, the constitutional order of Ukraine from criminal encroachments, ensuring peace and security of mankind, as well as the prevention of criminal offenses" [4, p. 6]. Based on the requirements of this article, the prevention of criminal offenses is one of the goals of criminal punishment. Its content is to influence non-law-abiding citizens because of the threat of punishment, thereby preventing them from committing criminal offenses. Consequently, the study of criteria for increasing the effectiveness of

the norms of criminal law in the prevention of criminal offenses is one of the areas of the fight against crime.

The results of the analysis of scientific publications. The scientific article is based on the analysis of the legislation of Ukraine, as well as the views of domestic and foreign scientists on the punishment for a committed criminal offense and its effectiveness in preventing new criminal offenses. In particular, Russian scientists I.P. Lanovenko, P.P. Mikhailenko, V.I. Shakun and others. Among foreign experts in this field, I. Andenes, B. Kholyst, E.M. Shura, V. Fox. There is no doubt that their research is a significant contribution to criminology and criminal law, but they do not exhaust all the key and individual issues of the topic. The questions that arose with the adoption in 2001 of the new edition of the Criminal Code of Ukraine require further theoretical development.

The purpose of the article is to analyze the norms of criminal law from the point of view of their preventive affect, the impact of changes in criminal legislation on the effectiveness of criminal law in preventing criminal offenses, as well as analyzing the criteria for increasing the effectiveness of criminal law in preventing criminal offenses.

Presentation of the main material. To increase the effectiveness of the norms of criminal law in the prevention of crime, it is important to coordinate the sanctions for committing a certain type of criminal offenses with sanctions for other criminal offenses. The criminal law should contain clear instructions on the rules of individualization of responsibility and the possible boundaries of legal proceedings in their implementation [5, p. 143]. This is dictated by the presence in society of a certain hierarchy of social values, which should also be reflected in the severity of measures taken for violation of these values. Any person guilty of committing criminal offenses should be subject to the minimum punishment necessary to correct him, prevent him from committing new criminal

offenses, to influence other unstable people, and to satisfy a sense of justice.

At present, the problem of combating organized crime has become acute in society. Organized crime, which embodies the highest form of crime development, now has a pronounced transnational character. It continues to conquer and monopolize more and more spheres of public life in almost every state, providing itself with high profits. In this regard, we agree with A.I. Shinalskiy that the fight against organized crime is associated with a number of criminal law, criminal procedure and organizational problems and requires the improvement of the current national legislation. One of the most important areas of countering organized crime is the strengthening of punitive sanctions for the commission of criminal offenses by organized criminal groups and increasing the responsibility of persons involved in organized crime.

With regard to the strengthening of punitive sanctions in countering criminal offenses, it is proposed to consider the death penalty as a relatively permissible punishment, which may be a necessary punitive means of combating crime in the presence of certain socio-economic prerequisites for this and inappropriate under other conditions [6, p. 14-15].

To increase the effectiveness of the norms of criminal law, it is necessary to expand the procedural status of a victim of a criminal offense, since the central procedural figure of criminal proceedings should be the victim of a criminal offense, not a criminal. Without such a reform of the criminal process, the adoption of any measures to strengthen the fight against crime will not give positive results [7, p. 78].

For a more complete and objective study of the effectiveness of criminal law in the prevention of crime, it is necessary to systematically conduct research and generalization of the practice of implementing the current legislation.

Increasing the effectiveness of the

norms of criminal law in the prevention of crimes can be achieved in parallel ways:

- 1) carrying out a criminological examination of all accepted norms of criminal law;
- 2) conducting a sociological survey of the population on the most important and relevant norms of criminal law.

Planning for the implementation of a system of measures to prevent criminal offenses is now becoming an integral part of plans for the socio-economic development of a production team, settlement, district, city, region. An urgent task for criminologists is to create standard sections of these plans, in which all areas of preventive activity, the whole range of measures to prevent criminal offenses would be linked into an organic whole, all the best that was created by theory and practice was embodied, and has passed the test of time.

A prerequisite for planning all types of preventive activities for a more or less long period is the development of reliable methods for predicting crime. Criminological forecasts, in turn, are impossible without a constant deep study of crime, identification of its patterns and development trends, the reasons for changes in its structure and dynamics. The reliability of mid-term and long-term forecasts of changes in the dynamics of crime can be ensured only with the maximum use of forecasts of the development of social phenomena that have a criminogenic and anti-criminogenic nature.

Improving the system for increasing crime prevention requires the combined efforts of criminologists researching different problems. It is important to ensure the fundamental unity of the basic conceptual provisions and conceptual apparatus, the consistency of research programs, the comparability of their results, the possible unification of their methods and tools. At the same time, it is hardly possible to develop proposals for improving and increasing the efficiency of the crime prevention system only by the efforts of lawyers. In order to ensure fruitful

research results, it is necessary to use all the opportunities that open up at the intersection of different sciences. One such problem is the prevention of antisocial behavior. Lawyers probably not only cannot but should not study many of its aspects on their own.

The organization and legal support of crime prevention activities in modern conditions should, to a greater extent than before, take into account the economic, demographic, socio-cultural and other heterogeneity of the country. The preventive direction of modern criminal policy is that all new social relations that need criminal law protection are included in the sphere of its activity. This, first of all, concerns the criminal law regulation of social relations associated with illegal enrichment. For example, currently in Ukraine there is a tendency when a criminal offense becomes just a way to achieve economic success, and destructive economic factors have become the main factor in the growth of crime.

It should be noted here that there is experience in the development of legal norms of a direct preventive nature. In the 70s of the last century in the USSR, the Regulations on strongholds of order protection, Regulations on councils for prevention in labor collectives, Regulations on the preventive service of internal affairs bodies were put into effect. The implementation of these norms had a positive effect on increasing the effectiveness of the norms of criminal law in the prevention of crimes.

Based on the foregoing, it can be concluded that the increase in the effectiveness of the norms of criminal law in the prevention of criminal offenses is determined, first of all, by a number of objective reasons caused by the need to adopt a new norm of criminal law or change the existing one. The norms of criminal law, like the norms of other branches of law, inevitably lose their relevance, cease to correspond to their own purpose in connection with the continuous development of public life. A prerequisite for improving the norms of criminal law is a change in the na-

ture and state of crime in specific historical conditions.

In order to improve the scientific level and quality of preparation of legislative acts, it is advisable to adopt the Law "On criminological examination of draft laws", as well as to organize leading scientific and higher educational institutions of Ukraine specializing in the problems of combating crime and security, scientific discussions and criminological examination of prepared draft laws. The results of such discussions and examinations should be sent to the Verkhovna Rada for an appropriate response.

In our opinion, public opinion can be defined as one of the ways of the existence of public consciousness through a value judgment that expresses an attitude towards events, phenomena of public life and consists in the approval or condemnation of the latter. It should be noted that public opinion is a phenomenon, the properties of which are very diverse, but have not been sufficiently studied, especially those of them that make it possible to use this opinion to prevent criminal offenses. It is characteristic that the warning of public opinion comes out in cases when it contains a negative assessment not only of antisocial manifestations, but also of the personality of the violator of the criminal norm.

The strength of public opinion as a criterion for increasing the effectiveness of criminal law in the prevention of crimes lies precisely in the fact that it is a combination of value judgment and freedom of the people. If this is absent, then the norms of criminal law will not have a preventive function. Thus, various questionnaires and polls indicate that the majority of Ukrainian citizens believe that the murderer deserves to be executed [8, p. 9]. In particular, according to our survey, 60.78% of respondents are convinced that the abolition of the death penalty in Ukraine contributes to an increase in the number of premeditated murders, and 80.4% believe that its introduction again would have a preventive value [9, p. 53].

At the same time, legislators - deputies,

whom the people entrusted with the protection of their interests, in spite of the latter, decide the opposite. This divergence of opinion between the people and the legislators came to be considered a democracy. However, if this issue were brought up for public discussion, then real democracy would have been obtained, in particular, the function of protecting articles of criminal law would have found its manifestation. Consequently, the provisions of Art. 69 of the Constitution of Ukraine that “the expression of the will of the people is carried out through elections, referendum and other forms of direct democracy” was not taken into account in this case.

But legislation should be a complete reflection of the will of the people. For example, in Belarus, where 80% of citizens approve of the death penalty, this principle is taken into account [10, p. 98]. Therefore, the Criminal Code of the Republic of Belarus retains the death penalty, but it is not provided as the only possible punishment for a particular crime for which it can be imposed. An alternative to the death penalty is life imprisonment and imprisonment for up to 25 years.

Society often becomes particularly “sensitive” to a particular category of criminal offenses, either because of their prevalence or under the influence of the media that involve them. For example, public attention is drawn to the issues of contract killings, illegal drug trade, drug addiction among young people, but, unfortunately, the state does little to deal with the problems of corruption. Public opinion in this area is also at a low level.

Are there any limits to the use of public opinion as a factor in the effectiveness of the norms of criminal law in the prevention of criminal offenses? This question should be answered in the affirmative. Such limits exist, and the reason for this is as follows: if crime prevention goes beyond the limits of expediency, degenerating into repression, then public opinion will not support this rule of law.

Public opinion about law and criminal offenses (public interest in the problems of

crime and its overcoming, the activities of law enforcement agencies, etc.) should always be taken into account when developing and adopting new laws.

Law enforcement agencies can count on comprehensive assistance from the population only when they enjoy authority. The latter is ensured, in particular, by objectivity and honesty, high rates of detection of criminal offenses, etc.

Information mechanisms (mass media), becoming a concentrated expression of public opinion, are a reliable tool for public protection of society from crime.

To increase the effectiveness of the norms of criminal law in the prevention of crimes, there must be conditions. The main theoretical premise for determining the conditions for increasing the effectiveness of criminal law in the prevention of criminal offenses is a systematic study of articles of the Criminal Code of Ukraine, mandatory forecasting of the consequences of the adoption of these norms. and, equally important, the study of existing law enforcement practice.

The effectiveness of the norms of criminal law in the prevention of crimes can come only when this norm is adopted and acts in accordance with a certain economic and social policy of the state. In turn, only that norm, the content of which has been fully clarified, can be correctly applied. A simplified understanding of the content of a norm, its leveling lead to non-observance of the principle of systematic expression of criminal law norms in legislation, which is associated with a violation of the logic of the internal structure of the latter.

The criterion for the effectiveness of the norms of criminal law in the prevention of crime is the organizational support of the process of introducing amendments and additions to the Criminal Code of Ukraine, in particular, the solution of the issue of its conceptual certainty. The basis not only of the Criminal Code of Ukraine, but also of bills on amendments and additions to it should be based on the concept developed by a joint

commission consisting of deputies of the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine and leading experts in criminal law and approved by the Verkhovna Rada as law. Along with this, the development, discussion and adoption of bills on amendments and additions to the Criminal Code of Ukraine should be carried out with the participation of the best representatives of the scientific community.

This law, among other articles, should contain articles of the following content:

«Article ... Concept of the bill

The concept of the draft law contains an explanation of the system of fundamental ideas and rules, according to which the structure and composition and content of mutually agreed principles, institutions and norms of the law should be determined, as well as justify changes in the current legislation and simulate the consequences of the proposed changes».

«Article ... Expert examination of the draft law

To assess the quality of proposals in connection with the adoption of a new law or improvement of the current legislation, an independent scientific examination should be carried out. An independent scientific examination of the draft law is carried out by scientific institutions, higher educational institutions, leading scientists and specialists of the relevant profile».

In order to implement the idea of conducting a criminological examination of criminal law norms adopted in 1996-1997, a comprehensive methodology for criminological examination of draft legislative and other regulatory legal acts, management decisions was developed. In early 1998, the draft methodology was submitted to the Cabinet of Ministers for submission to the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine. However, unfortunately, no decision has yet been made on this issue.

Also, a condition for increasing the effectiveness of the norms of criminal law in the prevention of criminal offenses is the development of a mechanism for real control over

income, and even more so clarification of the origin of certain estates and the seizure of loot from the people. There is no doubt that this is extremely difficult, because it will affect professional criminals and, of course, first of all will hit the corrupt servants of the people who will do everything to block any significant proposals in this area. However, this is the path to be followed if we want to really fight organized crime.

Therefore, in our opinion, the following should be attributed to the main conditions for increasing the effectiveness of the norms of criminal law in the prevention of crimes:

1) mandatory forecasting of the consequences of the adoption of the norms of criminal law;

2) study of the existing law enforcement practice;

3) restriction in the Special Part of the Criminal Code of Ukraine of special offenses;

4) the development of a mechanism for real control over income, and even more so the clarification of the origin of some estates and the seizure of the plundered from the people;

5) elimination of imbalances in the structure of the Code, unjustified deviation from the typical construction of articles of its Special Part;

6) elimination of unjustified concentration in the dispositions of the norms enshrined in them, a number of acts, each of which, in principle, could constitute the content of a separate norm;

7) organizational support of the process of making amendments and additions to the Criminal Code of Ukraine, in particular, solving the issue of its conceptual certainty;

8) the adoption of a norm of criminal law in accordance with the current political, economic situation in the country, etc.

Conclusions. Based on the foregoing, it can be concluded that the criteria for increasing the effectiveness of criminal law in the prevention of criminal offenses are:

1) legal measures to increase the effec-

tiveness of the norms of criminal law in the prevention of criminal offenses;

2) public opinion as a factor in increasing the effectiveness of criminal law in the

prevention of criminal offenses;

3) the conditions for increasing the effectiveness of the norms of criminal law in the prevention of criminal offenses.

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